

Diagnostic Interviews

Question 1 - What are the problems faced in the development of the web applications?

- One developer said that the organization of the **flow-core-library** wasn't intuitive.
- Five developers complained about the time the test pipeline takes to complete.
- Two developers pointed out that the applications' end to end test suits had replicated code which caused them to take unnecessary steps and made maintenance difficult.
- One developer mentioned a loss of fluidity when he/she had to make changes on a shell application and the **flow-core-library** simultaneously, because it was necessary to recompile the library and restart the application.
- Two developers said that a change in the **flow-core-library** doesn't necessarily trigger the test pipeline of the applications. So unless the shell applications are updated, their pipeline might brake silently.
- Two developers mentioned that the way unit tests are being implemented is not paying of the time invested.

Question 2 - How easy is it to add new developers to the current development team? And how easy is it to add another development team to work in parallel on the same applications?

- Four developers found the applications' documentation lacking.
- Three developer said that it would take time for a new team member to understand how the application works.
- Six developers think that adding a second development team on the same application is hard and/or would require more coordination.
- Three developers affirmed that adding a second development team would be harder than adding a new member to the existing team.
- Two developers think that a work in parallel on the same application would require both teams to use the same development process and scrum board to reduce conflict and avoid knowledge islands.
- One developer said that the initial setup for adding a new teammate is hard, but afterwards it does not present many problems.

Question 3 - How would a greater division of the application into separate projects and libraries impact the team's capacity to integrate new developers or to work in parallel with another team?

- Two developers said that dividing the library would better limit the scope of each component.
- Six developers affirmed it would facilitate to teach someone new to learn about the applications.
- One developer said it would minimize the problem of knowledge islands because it would be easier to learn how the application works without the need of a tutor.
- One developer thinks it might reduce the effort to maintain the applications.
- Five developers raised a concern about a possible increased complexity on the maintenance of the projects if the split granularity is excessively fine.
- One developer raised a concern about how having a shared libraries might cause conflict between teams, since there isn't any API to limit what each team can modify.
- One developer said that breaking down the applications would be costly.
- One developer thinks a greater division would reduce the conflict between teams.
- One developer mentioned a loss of fluidity when developing libraries.

Question 4 - How easy is it to reuse the components we have today in new applications?

- One developer said that the components are almost ready for being reused.
- Two developer thinks the components could be changed to have a more generic use.
- One developer affirmed that the components have a well-defined scope.
- Three developers mentioned that the communication between components through messages that they use today reduces their coupling.
- Three developers mentioned that the components could be better separated into modules.
- One developer said that today we don't plan components to be reused and many of our components are similar or have replicated code.
- One developer thinks that a shared library for generic components might be helpful with code reuse.
- One developer affirmed that the coupling between components today is high.
- One developer said that part of the more generic components are ready for reuse.
- One developer mentioned that maintaining component retro-compatibility is costly.

Question 5 - What are the impacts of the application's current centralization of data?

- Four developers said that it reduces the chance of showing divergent information on different components.
- Three developers think it increases the coupling of the components.
- Two developers said that the service might be overloaded with data and could be broken down into services with better domain delimitation.
- One developer mentioned that the data centralization facilitates accessing the data of the whole system.

Question 6 - How would distributing the data management responsibilities between components impact on the applications?

- Two developers said that it would have to be done with caution in order to keep the consistency through all the applications.
- One developer suggested the need for additional automated tests.
- Four developers think it would reduce the coupling between components.
- One developer views it as an opportunity to make the scope of some components more generic.
- One developer raised a concern about confusing the members of the team with the different object interfaces this process would require.
- Two developers prefer to have the data centralized.
- One developer said that reacting to events would require an extra overhead.